

To the common (unified) field theory

Rostislav A. Taratuta*

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this paper is to introduce the new bosonic mechanism and new treatment of dark energy.

a) The hypothesis on dark energy as the energy of a postulated dark field was made, and a combined gravitational-dark field was introduced. This field is the key to a specified approach and highlights the possibility for gauge boson to obtain mass not by means of interaction with Higgs boson, but by interacting with a massive scalar mode of a single gravitational-dark field. The advantage of this approach over Higgs model is the manifest that the massless gauge boson acquires mass through interaction with massive combined gravitational-dark field, which acquires mass due to the spontaneous symmetry breaking. This allows the mechanism to account for the dark sector while Higgs model does not include dark sector; and

b) address a naturalness problem/hierarchy problem associated with Higgs theory.

In the theory account for the existence of hierarchy mass gap and changing symmetries (CPT violation is associated with) addresses the issue of the difference between energy density of dark energy and gauge boson masses.

c) The scalar term obtained in theory has properties consistent with the properties of Higgs scalar.

d) Also predicted existence of dark boson as a quant of postulated dark field and point out on testability of the suggested mechanism.

e) Communicates how masses for fermions arise and reproduced the fermionic mixing angle within the theoretical framework.

f) Quantitative estimate about how the model could predict cancellation differences in energy scales between the energy density of dark energy and gauge boson masses presented.

Specifically, a scale factor of CPT invariance $\sim 10^{14}$ GeV account for the cancellation.

Constraint on the 'Higgs like' mass of 100 GeV determines the value of the energy density of dark energy 10^{-12} eV.

g) Mathematical proof that the theory Lagrangian corresponds to special cases for Lagrangian to be renormalizable presented. The proof of renormalizability is reduced to the proof of the correspondence Lagrangian of the theory, to the special type of renormalizable Lagrangians valid in five dimensions.

h) Specified cases at what point the equations of the mechanism and general relativity theory coincide.

i) Address dark matter(particle): The structure constitutes the gravitational part(mass)—the dark part(tunnel). The whole structure is not charged because the symmetry is global but charged because the spontaneous breaking of local symmetry.

j) Treatment baryon asymmetry presented.

k) The underlying common(unified) connections are denoted and represent key connections underlying theory postulates.

These relationships outline an experiment to prove the presented theory in combine electromagnetic:

spin 0 mode - testing the appearance of the gravity manipulation effect due to a dark boson with negative energy \bar{E} (namely, with negative gravitational mass and positive inertial mass); and spin 2 mode - the detection of the gravitational wave as an experimentally measured value.

By pointing out the experimental testability of the existence of a dark boson with the noted properties, the theory manifests a violation of the equivalence principle in general relativity. Also pointed out the process of restoring global symmetry in the mechanism.

Keyword(s): Unified field theories and models; Quantum mechanics

PACS number(s): 12.10.-g; 03.65.-w

* Corresponding author. E-mail address: r.tr@verizon.net (R.Taratuta)

I. INTRODUCTION

At present within Standard model of particle physics exist Higgs mechanism [1], which explains obtaining mass by gauge bosons.

The current paper addressed the possibility to suggest another approach in Sec. I to the problem of obtaining masses by gauge bosons [2].

➤ The need for it dictated because of Higgs mechanism:

i) incorporates the existence of substantial physical and mathematical flaws explicitly related to it and outlined in the comparison between two mechanisms presented in Sec. II;

ii) has a naturalness problem/hierarchy problem associated with it;

iii) does not include dark sector.

While predictions of the suggested mechanism can be proven according to the process of any theory vindication the proposed new approach can address all three weakness of Higgs theory.

↵ The primary purpose of the paper is to support of feasibility presented arguments and is the comparison between two mechanisms the noted (new bosonic) mechanism and Higgs mechanism while physical and mathematical differences between two approaches specified. It was considered that work by [3] should foster another model for obtaining nonzero masses by fundamental particles.

While negative conclusions regarding construction of consistent interacting theories of higher spin in a form of the gauge theory of several coupled or self-coupled fields were outlined [4], it is noted that spontaneous breakdown of the unacceptable symmetries is a possibility in order to evade these difficulties (ref. ‘The meaning of the spontaneous symmetry breaking’, below).

The emphasized original hypothesis behind suggested alternative approach mainly constitutes:

A) Dark field.

P1. Postulate: Dark energy determines the existence of a dark field.

B) Curvature of spacetime (the pseudo-Riemannian metric).

P2. Postulate: Gravitational and dark fields compose a single gravitational – dark field.

In Sec. I presented

➤ ‘The essence of the mechanism’ is:

i. Massless gravitational-dark field acquires mass due to the spontaneous symmetry breaking and the contribution of matter;

‘the meaning of the spontaneous symmetry breaking’ and its relevance to Elitzur theorem [5] is emphasized as follows:

1. As specified by the proposed approach there are two paths for spontaneous symmetry breaking, namely, direct and restoring.

a) In direct path:

symmetry breaking mechanism is analogous to the standard approach [6] with Elitzur constraint, i.e., spontaneously breaking global symmetry; explicitly breaking of local symmetry by a gauge fixing term, ref. eqs. (0.1.1) and (0.1.2).

Thus, equations of the proposed theory formally coincide with standard theory equations although the physics are very different.

As outlined in paragraph ‘The essence of the mechanism’, the first stage(i) of this process leads to mass appearance in dark sector and the second stage(ii) leads to mass appearance in gravitational (metric) sector. This process corresponds to moving gauge field from ‘mixed’ state at the first stage (coupled with gravitational-dark scalar mode) to ‘pure’ state at the second stage (decoupled from gravitational-dark tensor mode). This results in obtaining gauge bosons mass by means of application of a two- stage schema.

b) In restoring path:

There is a restoring force (due to dark sector in reference to dark energy), which restores the symmetry from local to global. In this context restoring means cancellation of gauge field in eq. (0.1.2), so there is no gauge fixing anymore, thus no spontaneous breaking of local symmetry can occur. State of symmetry is therefore restored to global, ref. eq. (0.1.1).

This process corresponds to moving gauge field from ‘pure’ (-split) state (decoupled from gravitational-dark tensor mode) back to ‘mixed’ state (coupled with gravitational-dark scalar mode). This results in losing mass by gauge bosons and returning into massless form.

2. In the context of local symmetry, the spontaneous symmetry breaking means that the state of gauge field spontaneously changes from ‘mixed’ to ‘pure’, thus explicitly breaking local symmetry by gauge fixing term on a) –path; the state of gauge field can also spontaneously change from ‘pure’ to ‘mixed’, thus restoring the state of global symmetry by restoring force on b) –path).

ii. Massless vector bosons acquire mass due to the interaction with a massive gravitational-dark field.

In Sec. II presented

➤ The description of the symmetry breaking process as:

i. To the role which the electromagnetic field plays within the presented theory framework, noted its compliance with Elitzur theorem, also

1.introduced mathematical formalism of the theory postulates.

a) Under paragraph ‘Before symmetry breaking’ (i.e., the electro-magnetic field exists in ‘mixed’ state) specified mechanism of *obtaining mass by dark component- the first channel*, while gravitational component exists as massless; considered case without matter because there is no matter contribution to the mass in dark sector.

b) Under paragraph ‘After symmetry breaking’ (i.e., the electro-magnetic field exists in ‘pure’ state) specified mechanism of *obtaining mass by gravitational field - the first channel*.

c) The appearance of the massive gravitational field determines *the second channel* (in addition to the first channel) *of the source of mass for a dark field*, namely the coupling between massive dark field and vacuum metric tensor is described by Klein- Gordon eq. for gravitational interaction action.

d) Then evaluated the contribution of matter in a mass term for the gravitational field. This determines *the second channel of the source of mass for the gravitational field*, namely the appearance of a mass for the gravitational – dark field is due to stress-energy tensor factor. In this case, DVZ discontinuity disappears in covariant limit thus reflecting the fact that massive gravitational-dark field in covariant form couples to matter.

2. The following paragraph ‘Model of boson masses’ pointed out in the process assigning mass to vector gauge bosons by massive gravitational-dark field due to coupling process.

ii. Presented corresponding Lagrangian for the theory and the symmetries for each paragraph mentioned above.

In Sec. III presented results and discussion of the suggested new approach.

➤ Presented explanation of each term in Lagrangian of the theory from the standpoint of contribution to the masses of gauge bosons.

In Sec. IV presented conclusion of the theory; and

➤ Also emphasized prediction of the existence of dark boson, which in turn can be considered as a possibility to vindicate suggested mechanism experimentally.

In Appendix different subject related to the validation of the suggested mechanism addressed.

➤ This section starts with a paragraph, which explains how masses for fermions arise within the theoretical framework.

Then in the paragraph on symmetries Lagrangian of the presented theory outlined the proof of renormalizability.

Addressing naturalness problem/hierarchy problem within the theoretical framework formulated in the paragraph on Mass scale structure.

The last paragraph on fermionic mixing angle communicates the connection between noted theory and Standard model electroweak sector.

II. THEORY

0. Model of gravitational-dark field masses.

This paper introduces the mechanism based on two postulates: P1, P2.

Further consideration is presented below and is focused on the role which the electromagnetic field plays in the schema.

The main purpose of the paper is the comparison between the noted (new bosonic) mechanism and Higgs mechanism. Following is the analysis of these mechanisms:

1. Higgs mechanism.

a) application of Elitzur theorem to Higgs theory leads to the conclusion that Higgs field does not have expectation value and as a result cannot spontaneously break symmetry;

b) the analysis outlined in Higgs model presentation in [7] where the main focus of the analysis is on the usage of unitary gauge, which assumes the elimination of ‘ghost field’; however, proving renormalizability of this model is provided in ‘tHooft gauge requiring reintroduction of the ‘ghost field’.

This two contradictory mathematical procedures which are required to prove Higgs model demonstrate the necessity of introducing the driving force to restore the state of maximum symmetry from the state of symmetry breaking.

Presence of virtual particles (quantum fluctuations) associated with the ‘ghost field’ leads to instability of vacuum solution in Higgs model (in the framework presented in the paper this discrepancy addressed by referencing the second law of thermodynamics which states that entropy must increase so as to reach the state with maximum symmetry, ref. ‘the special symmetry evolution principle’, [8]).

2. The new bosonic mechanism.

The scalar term obtained within the scope of the presented approach is consistent in action of assigning mass to vector gauge boson with the corresponding result obtained by means of Higgs scalar (ref. chapter ‘Results and Discussion’ , item **v. a)** below).

The dark energy, which is the driving force, increases the volume, which leads to the state with more entropy, i.e. symmetry. This driving force is determined by the requirement to cancel local vacuum fluctuations (ref. on restoring ‘vacuum state’, below).

As Weyl’s conjecture associates gauge with a local symmetry and the change of phase with $U(1)$ gauge symmetry, the electromagnetic field appears as a result of quantum mechanical consideration of the wave function of a charged particle.

The electromagnetic field, which appears as a result of the above-mentioned process, is presented in ‘mixed’ and ‘pure’ states, which accordingly correspond to the cases ‘Before symmetry breaking’ (ref. eq. (0.1.1) as ‘Lagrangian for non-interaction’) and ‘After symmetry breaking’ (ref. eq. (0.1.2) as ‘Lagrangian for interaction’) below.

➤ A ‘pure’ state assumes interaction between electromagnetic field and system; a ‘mixed’ state is represented as the superposition state of composite system including electromagnetic field.

Following approach specifies tensor-gravitational::dark field $\eta(x)$ as a single field and dark energy as energy of a dark field and can formulate a mechanism for obtaining masses in bosonic systems.

1. Abelian symmetry breaking.

According to the standard approach to spontaneous symmetry breaking [5], the transition from a global symmetry of the system to a local symmetry is provided by introducing an interaction gauge field, i.e. electromagnetic field ϕ_i .

Interaction:

- i. Before symmetry breaking, vacuum state::tensor-gravitational::dark field $\Phi(x)$ is not coupled to an electromagnetic (gauge) field;
- ii. When symmetry is broken, the field $\Phi(x)$ is coupled to a gauge electromagnetic field.

The ‘vacuum’ state represents redundant degrees of freedom, i.e., it is manifestly associated with ‘mixed’ state of electromagnetic field (gauge field) and Goldstone boson. Thus, V is the expected value of the ‘vacuum’ state and appears as a result of gauge symmetry breaking, which, in this framework, means the following: the change of gauge structure (i.e., Landau phase transition with order parameter V), which results in change from ‘mixed’ to ‘pure’ state.

↖ without interacting with an electromagnetic field, i.e. before symmetry breaking (Mexican hat potential has a flat direction, corresponds to a U(1) model –Goldstone)

$$L(\Phi) = |\partial\Phi|^2 - \lambda(|\Phi|^2 - v^2)^2 \quad (0.1.1)$$

so $\Phi(x)$ corresponds to **1 i**);

↗ this model is an origin of appearance V at the ‘vacuum’ state, i.e. gives mass to the Goldstone-dark field (gapless excitation).

↘ interacting with an electromagnetic field, i.e. after symmetry breaking (transforms from symmetries Lagrangian invariant with respect to global symmetry from a U(1) group – Abelian to one invariant with respect to local symmetry or gauge-invariant)

$$L(\Phi, \phi) = -\frac{1}{4}F^{ik}F_{ik} + |D\Phi|^2 - \lambda(|\Phi|^2 - v^2)^2 \quad (0.1.2)$$

where,

$$F_{ik} = \partial_i\phi_k - \partial_k\phi_i;$$

ϕ_i is a covariant four-potential of the electromagnetic field;

the interaction with photons via minimal substitution ref. [9]

$$D_i\Phi = \partial_i\Phi + ie\phi_i\Phi;$$

so $\Phi(x)$ corresponds to **1 ii**);

↗ this model is an origin of appearance of only a massive gravitational field and a Goldstone-dark field (due to the massive Goldstone field).

$\left(\partial \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\sqrt{2}}, \sqrt{\lambda} \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{\lambda}}{\sqrt{2}}, v \rightarrow \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}} \right)$ substitutions eliminate the constant term

from the eq. (0.1.1) - (0.1.2).

1.1. Before symmetry breaking (due to the application of Goldstone theorem) .

The paper presented in this case the description of obtaining mass by dark (Goldstone-dark) field.

The theory, as presented here, will assume that the Goldstone field and a gravitational-dark field interact.

In this case, a scalar field is complex, applying scheme [5]:

$$\Phi(x) = \nu + \xi(x) + i\eta(x) \quad (1.1)$$

where, $\xi(x)$ - 'vacuum' state (coincides with Goldstone field);

$\eta(x)$ - gravitational –dark field is complex due to the interaction with a Goldstone field (addresses to Goldstone theorem):

$$\eta(x) = h(x) - i\Xi(x) \quad (1.1 a)$$

It is normally assumed that:

$h(x)$ - gravitational field part , i.e. massless tensor of second rank spin 2 field;

$\Xi(x)$ - dark field part, i.e. massless scalar spin 0 field (dark boson);

➤ note the negative sign before the second term, which points out that dark energy is negative.

When substituting eq. (1.1 a) in eq. (1.1), the following is obtained (addresses to Elitzur theorem):

$$\Phi(x) = \nu + \xi(x) + \Xi(x) + ih(x) \quad (1.1 b)$$

FP. symmetries Lagrangian in a form is (for notation (ref. eqs. (A 2.1))):

➤ without interaction with the electromagnetic field ϕ_i (here and further under interaction with ϕ_i assume a 'pure' state);

$$L_{FP} = k^2 (A_{ik})^2 + \left(\frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \right)^2 - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}}{\partial x_s} - \frac{3}{4} k^2 C^2 - \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} \quad (1.2.1 a)$$

for massless ($k_h = 0, k_\zeta = 0$) gravitational and dark fields obtain:

$$L_{FP} = \left(\frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \right)^2 - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}}{\partial x_s} - \frac{3}{8} \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} \quad (1.2.1 b)$$

➤ According to the superposition principle, if an auxiliary scalar field can exist in states described by ξ and Ξ , then it can exist in a state described by the Goldstone-dark field

$$\zeta(x) = \xi(x) + \Xi(x)$$

Viz., further refers to a dark field, however, where it is appropriate to assume it rather refers to the Goldstone-dark field.

Referring to eqs. (0.1.1) and (1.1 b) leads to (using $h-\zeta$ notation to be intact with eq. (A 2.2.1 below)):

$$L = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_i \zeta)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(\partial_i h)^2 - \frac{1}{2}\lambda v^2 \zeta^2 - \frac{1}{2}\lambda v \zeta (\zeta^2 + h^2) - \frac{1}{8}\lambda (\zeta^2 + h^2)^2 \quad (1.3 a)$$

where, a shifted Goldstone-dark field is defined as:

$$\zeta(x) = v + \xi(x) + \Xi(x) \quad (1.3 b)$$

$$v = \pm \sqrt{\frac{-k_{\zeta-h}^2}{\lambda}}$$

λ - self - interaction coupling constant;

$k_{\zeta-h}$ - mass for $\Phi(x)$ ($k_{\zeta-h}^2 < 0$);

In case of $v < 0$, it corresponds to dark energy; if $v > 0$, it corresponds to gravitational energy.

\succ addressing gravitational (gauge) and dark (non-gauge) fields reflects the fact that bosonic mechanism does not follow from a gauge principle.

Thus obtain massless (k_h) for h and mass ($k_\zeta \equiv \sqrt{\lambda}v$) for ζ .

It is presented that the Goldstone field and the dark field in fact are two real Klein-Gordon fields.

\succ k_Ξ appears as a result of obtaining mass by a dark field, i.e. $k_\Xi = k_\zeta$; ansatz Goldstone boson does not disappear.

i. No matter.

It is demonstrated by the results described above that matter directly contributes only to the mass of gravitational field;

1.1.0. Massless gravitational and dark fields (before symmetry breaking).

Viz., eq. (1.6 below), obtain FP eq. for **Re** $\Phi(x)$ and **Im** $\Phi(x)$ parts in eq. (1.1 b).

For rest-mass $k_\zeta = 0$, $k_\Xi = 0$ (massless spin 0 scalar field), **Re** $\Phi(x)$ part represented for $\Xi(x)$ as:

\succ (ref. A_{ik} defined by eqs. (A 2.1 below), in case $\phi_i = 0$ no coupling between $\langle g^{ik} \rangle$ and dark boson exists);

$$-\square \left(\frac{1}{4} \delta_{ik} C \right) - \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x_i \partial x_k} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \left(\frac{1}{4} \delta_{ik} C \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_k} \left(\frac{1}{4} \delta_{ii} C \right) = 0 \quad (1.3.0 a)$$

i.e. inline with the Einstein eq. without matter.

Im $\Phi(x)$ part represented by the Fierz-Pauli eq. for massless spin 2 field as:

\succ (ref. A_{ik} defined by eqs. (A 2.1), in case $\phi_i = 0$ corresponds to absence of h_{ik} in A_{ik});

$$\frac{\partial^2 A_{lk}}{\partial x_l \partial x_k} + \frac{\partial^2 A_{li}}{\partial x_l \partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1.3.0 \text{ b})$$

if choosing a gauge to satisfy $\frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_i} = 0$, reduced to zero.

1.2. After symmetry breaking (due to the application of Elitzur theorem).

The paper presents the description of obtaining mass by massless gravitational field and the appearance of Nambu-Goldstone boson.

Following is a presentation of obtaining masses by gravitational and dark components of a combined gravitational-dark field as a result of spontaneous breaking of local symmetry and application of Fierz-Pauli approach [3] in sub-cases:

i. Force-free.

1.2.0. Obtaining masses for gravitational and dark fields.

It corresponds to the interaction of the gravitational field and the Goldstone field with the electromagnetic field ϕ_i .

Then continue to the mechanism of obtaining masses for spin 2 and spin 0 fields, as a result of symmetry breaking.

\prec (dark field does not interact, i.e. $\zeta \mapsto \xi$)

$$i\Pi_k = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} - ie\phi_k \quad (1.4.0)$$

$$f_{ik} = \Pi_i \Pi_k - \Pi_k \Pi_i = i \left\{ \frac{\partial \phi_k}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial x_k} \right\}$$

FP. symmetries Lagrangian in a form is:

\succ with interaction with electromagnetic field ϕ_i ;

(1.4.1 a)

$$L_{FP} = k^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik} + \Pi_l A_{ik} \Pi_l^* A_{ik}^* - 2\Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_s^* A_{sk}^* + f_{ir} A_{rk} A_{ik}^* + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_k^* C^* + \Pi_r^* A_{rk}^* \Pi_k C \right\} - \frac{3}{4} k^2 C^* C - \frac{3}{8} \Pi_l C \Pi_l^* C^*$$

for massless spin 2 field interaction with an electromagnetic field is obtained:

$$\succ (k_h = 0, k_\xi = 0);$$

(1.4.1 b)

$$L_{FP} = \Pi_l A_{ik} \Pi_l^* A_{ik}^* - 2\Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_s^* A_{sk}^* + f_{ir} A_{rk} A_{ik}^* + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_k^* C^* + \Pi_r^* A_{rk}^* \Pi_k C \right\} - \frac{3}{8} \Pi_l C \Pi_l^* C^*$$

then for h, ξ fields the following is obtained:

(1.4.1 c)

$$L_{FP} = \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} + e^2 \phi_l^2 A_{ik} A_{ik}^* - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} - 2e^2 \phi_r \phi_s A_{rk} A_{sk}^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} + \frac{1}{2} e^2 \phi_r \phi_k A_{rk} C^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} + \frac{1}{2} e^2 \phi_r \phi_k A_{rk}^* C - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l} - \frac{3}{8} e^2 \phi_l^2 C C^* + i \left\{ \begin{aligned} & e\phi_l A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} - e\phi_l A_{ik} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} - 2e\phi_s A_{sk}^* \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} + 2e\phi_r A_{rk} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} + A_{rk} A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial \phi_r}{\partial x_i} - A_{rk} A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial \phi_l}{\partial x_r} + \frac{1}{2} e\phi_k C^* \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} - \\ & \frac{1}{2} e\phi_r A_{rk} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} - \frac{1}{2} e\phi_k C \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} + \frac{1}{2} e\phi_r A_{rk}^* \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} - \frac{3}{8} e\phi_l C^* \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} + \frac{3}{8} e\phi_l C \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Adheres to the Mexican hat potential, i.e. to the case of unstable equilibrium and in reference to eqs. (0.1.1) \mapsto (0.1.2), obtain ((omitted terms cubic and quartic in fields h, ζ, ϕ_i),

(using $h-\zeta$ notation to be intact with eq. (A 2.2.2 below)) :

(1.5)

$$L = -\frac{1}{4} F_{ik} F^{ik} + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_i \zeta)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_i h + e\nu \phi_i)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \lambda \nu^2 \zeta^2 - \frac{1}{2} \lambda \nu \zeta (\zeta^2 + h^2) - \frac{1}{8} \lambda (\zeta^2 + h^2)^2$$

where,

\succ coupling to a composite spin 1 field, i.e. electromagnetic and B_i , leads to an expression for electromagnetic field:

$$F_{ik} = i(\Pi_i \phi_k - \Pi_k \phi_i), \quad i\Pi_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} - iB_i \quad (\text{in force-free case than } i\Pi_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i});$$

for spin 1 B_i field, the following is obtained:

$$\wp_{ik} = i(\Pi_i B_k - \Pi_k B_i), \quad i\Pi_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} - i\phi_i.$$

Thus obtain mass ($k_h \equiv$) $e\nu$ for h and mass ($k_\zeta \equiv$) $\sqrt{\lambda\nu}$ for ζ .

$$\succ h \mapsto \phi_i + \frac{1}{e\nu} \partial_i h \quad (\equiv z_i);$$

when Ricci theorem is applied for tensor analysis the following is obtained:

$$\phi_i + \frac{1}{e\nu \langle g_{ik} \rangle} \partial_i h_{ik} \quad (\equiv z_i).$$

Therefore, a massive gravitational field with mass k_h and a massive Goldstone-dark field with mass k_ζ is obtained.

\succ the k_ζ is not related to ϕ_i , i.e., it does not contain charge e since dark field does not interact with an electromagnetic field; k_ζ appears as a result of obtaining mass by Goldstone boson, i.e. $k_\xi = k_\zeta$.

1.2.1. Force-free eq.

Mass term for dark field appears as a result for the coupling between massive dark field and vacuum metric tensor (this coupling exists because the source of dark field is stress-energy tensor for scalar field).

Then Fierz-Pauli eq. for Ξ massive spin 0 field without interaction is

$$2k^2 A_{ik} - 2\Box A_{ik} + 2 \left\{ \frac{\partial^2 A_{sk}}{\partial x_s \partial x_i} + \frac{\partial^2 A_{si}}{\partial x_s \partial x_k} - \frac{1}{2} \delta_{ik} \frac{\partial^2 A_{rs}}{\partial x_r \partial x_s} \right\} - \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x_i \partial x_k} + \frac{1}{4} \delta_{ik} \Box C = 0 \quad (1.6)$$

$$-\frac{3}{2} k^2 C + \frac{3}{4} \Box C - \frac{\partial^2 A_{rk}}{\partial x_r \partial x_k} = 0$$

thus, satisfies P2.

As the appearance of the spin 0 field is described by Klein-Gordon eq., then referring to the massive spin 0 field, i.e. $\Xi(x)$ in eq. (1.1 b), leads to (ref. Klein-Gordon eq.):

$$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_i \left(\langle g^{ik} \rangle \sqrt{-g} \partial_k \Xi \right) + k_\Xi^2 \Xi = 0 \quad (1.6.1 a)$$

therefore, dark boson acquires a mass ($k_{\Xi} \neq 0$) and is coupled with gravitational potential field $\langle g^{ik} \rangle$; this coupling between $\langle g^{ik} \rangle$ and dark boson ($k_{\Xi} \neq 0$, so no singularity appears) is originated, as the source of the Ξ field is the stress-energy tensor for scalar field, which satisfies the Klein-Gordon eq.

$$T^{ik} = \frac{1}{k_{\Xi}} \left(\langle g^{i\alpha} \rangle \langle g^{k\beta} \rangle + \langle g^{i\beta} \rangle \langle g^{k\alpha} \rangle - \langle g^{ik} \rangle \langle g^{\alpha\beta} \rangle \right) \partial_{\alpha} \Xi^* \partial_{\beta} \Xi - \langle g^{ik} \rangle k_{\Xi} \Xi^* \Xi \quad (1.6.1 \text{ b})$$

\succ as a gradient of scalar can describe only particles of spin 0, and applying analogous to the Lorentz condition for a dark field part (as for gravitational definition, [3]), the following is obtained:

the description of the connection between Φ and dark energy

$$T^{ik} = -\langle g^{ik} \rangle k_{\Xi} \Xi^* \Xi \propto \langle g^{ik} \rangle$$

(as in dark energy definition [10]); thus obeying P1.

Above ref. to Ξ not ζ as Goldstone field, because ζ origin is different.

$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_i \langle g^{ik} \rangle \sqrt{-g} \partial_k \mapsto$ two-dimensional Laplacian on the vortex sheet $\tilde{x}^{\mu}(\sigma)$ ref. [11]; under $g \rightarrow -g$.

ii. Model of masses for gravitational and dark fields (contribution of matter).

According to this mechanism, mass for the gravitational field appears directly as a result of Ξ stress – energy tensor.

In this case, DVZ discontinuity disappears in covariant limit thus reflecting the fact that massive gravitational-dark field in covariant form couples to matter.

Following is a presentation of obtaining masses by gravitational and dark components of a combined gravitational-dark field as a result of the interaction with matter.

Ansatz symmetries Lagrangian viz., [12], [13]

$$L = L_{FP} + L_{\varphi} + \left\{ k_h h_{ik} T^{ik}(\varphi) + h_{ik} T^{ik}(h) \right\} + \{ h \leftrightarrow \zeta \} \quad (2.1)$$

where, L_{FP} is defined by eqs. (1.2.1).

\succ term $\{ h \leftrightarrow \zeta \}$ corresponds to $\{ \dots \}$ for h_{ik} with substitution by ζ ; for ζ part

$$l_{ik} = g_{ik} \underbrace{- \mathcal{E} \zeta}_{\mathcal{E} \Xi \langle g_{ik} \rangle}$$

$$\left(k_{\Xi}\Xi\langle g_{ik}\rangle T^{ik}(\varphi) + \Xi\langle g^{ik}\rangle T_{ik}(\Xi)\right)$$

where, $T_{ik}(\Xi)$ denoted by eq. (1.6.1 b).

Kinetic term L_{φ} for matter field φ acts as a mass term

$$L_{\varphi} = \frac{1}{2}\partial_i\varphi^*\partial^i\varphi \quad (2.2)$$

ref. [9].

$\succ m^2 = (\partial\varphi)^2$ - mass due to the contribution of the matter.

$h_{ik}T^{ik}(\varphi)$ term represents the massive spin 2 field h_{ik} , which couples with $T^{ik}(\varphi)$ like spin 2 boson, and DVZ discontinuity disappears in a covariant case, i.e. in the limit $k_{h,\Xi} \rightarrow 0$ obtains a spin 2 boson and a scalar dark boson, which couples with the stress-energy tensor(matter); as the stress-energy tensor is defined in a form

$$T^{ik}(\varphi) = -\partial^i\varphi\partial^k\varphi + \frac{1}{2}\iota^{ik}(\partial\varphi)^2 \quad (2.3)$$

where, in Minkovski space linear perturbation $\iota_{ik} = g_{ik} - \varepsilon h_{ik}$

ε - expansion parameter,

allows for vacuum metric $\iota_{ik} = \langle g_{ik} \rangle$; [14]

$$\sqrt{g} = \exp\left[\frac{1}{2}Tr \log(\iota_{ik} + \varepsilon h_{ik})\right] = \iota_{ii} + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon h_{ii}; \{h \leftrightarrow \zeta\}$$

$k = M_p^{-1}$ - coupling strength to the source T_{ik} (M_p - Planck mass).

\succ within the outlined mechanism, the disappearance of DVZ discontinuity is determined by the fact, that in 3D finite-mass relativistic bosons, characterized by BE condensation transition of the third order. For bosons of mass $O(10^{-32})$ eV, the condensation transition is indistinguishable from the second order related to massless relativistic bosons [15-16].

Consider

$$h_{ik}T^{ik}(\varphi) = -h_{ik}g_{\varphi}^{ik} + \frac{1}{2}h_{ik}g^{ik}(\partial\varphi)^2 - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon h^2(\partial\varphi)^2 \quad (2.4)$$

as a kinetic term of φ , which acts as a mass term for h_{ik} proportional to h^2 .

For $h-h$ field coupling is described by the term $h_{ik}T_{ik}(h)$

$$h_{ik}T_{ik}(h) = -h_{ik}\left(-\frac{1}{2}\partial_i h_{\rho\lambda}\partial_k h^{\rho\lambda} + \partial_i h_{\rho\lambda}\partial^{\rho}h_k^{\lambda} - \frac{1}{2}\partial_i h\partial^{\rho}h_{k\rho} - \frac{1}{2}\partial^{\rho}h\partial_i h_{k\rho} + \frac{1}{2}\partial_i h\partial^i h + \iota_{ik}L_{FP}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

where, $T_{ik}(h)$ -gravitational energy-momentum (stress-energy) tensor.

➤ the outlined mechanism does not contradict the Coleman-Mandula theorem [17], as consistency is preserved due to the fact that the gravitational-dark field contains only one spin 2 field (gravitational) and one spin 0 (dark) field.

Term linear in h_{ik} is removed:

$$g_{\varphi}^{ik} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ik} (\partial\varphi)^2 = 0 \quad (g_{ik} = g^{ik} - \text{Minkowski metric})$$

where, metric tensor is generated by matter [10]

$$g_{\varphi}^{ik} = \partial_i \varphi \partial_k \varphi;$$

and eq. (2.5) takes into account nonlinear effects.

Eq. (2.5) also takes into consideration massive [18] and massless or small-mass [19-22] self-interacting real scalar fields.

Diffeomorphism invariance is restored from the breaking state due to the contribution of the last term in (2.5). Structurally, this term incorporates local field fluctuations and the restoring path, both of which are attributed to the appearance of scalar field in eq. (1.2.1).

Local field fluctuations can point on the presence of Vainshtein-like behavior [23] within the scope of the presented mechanism. As far as the restoring path is concerned, the appearance of negative energy states associated with the existence of dark boson, can explain the appearance of ghost-like mode [24] in nonlinear Fierz –Pauli theory.

1.2.2. Model of boson masses (theory Lagrangian).

The paper outlines mechanism of assigning mass to the vector gauge bosons due to the interaction with a massive gravitational - dark field.

Resulted Lagrangian includes terms proportional to square of vector boson field (i.e., mass terms for vector bosons) as well as terms proportional to square of gravitational field and dark field parts of gravitational-dark field (i.e., mass terms corresponding to these parts).

Introduction of interactions: gravitational –dark - spin 1 field interaction.

Assume the interaction of a massive gravitational – dark field with a massless spin 1 field (i.e. vector field B_k):

$$i\Pi_k = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} - iB_k$$

(2.6.0)

$$f_{ik} = \Pi_i \Pi_k - \Pi_k \Pi_i = i \left\{ \frac{\partial B_k}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial B_i}{\partial x_k} \right\}$$

massless B_k coupling with massive (h_{ik}, ζ) , viz. FP. theory Lagrangian in a form

(2.6.1 a)

$$L_{FP} = k^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik} + \Pi_l A_{ik} \Pi_l^* A_{ik}^* - 2\Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_s^* A_{sk}^* + f_{ir} A_{rk} A_{ik}^* + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \Pi_r A_{rk} \Pi_k^* C^* + \Pi_r^* A_{rk}^* \Pi_k C \right\} - \frac{3}{4} k^2 C^* C - \frac{3}{8} \Pi_l C \Pi_l^* C^*$$

i.e. spin 1 field acquires mass as a result of the interaction with massive spin 2 and spin 0 fields;

where mixed $h_{ik} - \zeta$ terms also account for self interaction.

For h, ζ, B fields, the following is obtained:

(2.6.1 b)

$$L_{FP} = \left\{ k^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik} + \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} + B_l B_l^* A_{ik} A_{ik}^* - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} - 2 B_r B_s^* A_{rk} A_{sk}^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} B_r B_k^* A_{rk} C^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} + \frac{1}{2} B_r^* B_k A_{rk} C - \frac{3}{4} k^2 C^* C - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l} - \frac{3}{8} B_l B_l^* C C^* \right\} \\ + i \left\{ \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} A_{ik}^* B_l^* - A_{ik} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} B_l - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} A_{sk}^* B_s^* + 2 A_{rk} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} B_r + \frac{\partial B_r}{\partial x_i} A_{rk} A_{ik}^* - \frac{\partial B_l}{\partial x_r} A_{rk} A_{ik}^* \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} B_k^* C^* - \frac{1}{2} B_r A_{rk} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} B_k C + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} B_r^* A_{rk}^* - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} B_l^* C^* + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l} B_l C \right\}$$

\succ as a vector field mass term in theory Lagrangian is proportional to $B_l B_l^*$.

\therefore

Propagator for spin $s = 2$ field is derived as a sum over polarization states ε_{ik}^r times scalar propagator [9]

(3)

$$D_F^{ik\rho\sigma}(p) = \sum_r \varepsilon_r^{ik}{}^{*\rho\sigma}(p) \varepsilon_r{}^{\rho\sigma}(p) \Delta_F(p)$$

where, polarization tensor ε^r (polarization states ε_{ik}^r);

$\Delta_F(p)$ - scalar propagator.

The underlying geometry (ref. Fig. A4.1, below) corresponds to AdS₃ (Lorentzian analogue to hyperbolic space) geometry on the dark part and Lorentzian CFT on the gravitational part. In the physical vacuum (as denotes in ref. [2]) the process of creation of electron-(positron, hole) pair is defined by the process of absorption or emission of vector field ϕ_i .

State of this pair is ‘mixed’, which according to [25], stationary quantum kinetic equation for one-particle matrix for photon density will be:

$$i(\omega_v - \omega_v)N_{vv} = L_{vv}^{(p)} \{N, f\}$$

where, $L_{vv}^{(p)} \{N, f\}$ - collision operator; f - distribution function for light ($n = l$) and heavy ($n = h$) holes.

\succ the interaction between holes and the photons emitted by the holes during the transition from the heavy to light part of the energy spectrum are assumed to be weak; (holes are localized within the layer, with thickness $d \ll q_{\perp}^{-1}$)

description for photon emission is applicable where conditions

$$x \gg q_{\perp}^{-1}, l_{ph-p} \gg q_{\perp}^{-1}$$

are satisfied (l_{ph-p} – photon relaxation length in case of on-hole scattering).

The left hand inequality is satisfied where photons are registered in the far-field zone, while the right hand inequality eliminates from consideration the term specifying on-hole photon relaxation.

For Luttinger's isotropic model [26], the following is obtained for the Poynting's vector in $x < 0$ area:

(4)

$$\oint S_n^{(-)} ds = \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}\pi} \frac{e^2 \eta_-^{\frac{5}{2}} s}{V \hbar^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{v}_\perp \varepsilon^s m^2} \sin^2 \theta$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{q}} \omega_q^{\frac{1}{2}} \left\{ \left[k^2 (\bar{q} - \tilde{q})^2 + (k^2 - \bar{q}^2)(k^2 - \tilde{q}^2) \sin^2 kd \right] \frac{|a_l|^2}{\bar{q}^2 (k + \tilde{q})^2} + \frac{4k^2 |a_r|^2}{(k + \bar{q})^2} \right\}^2$$

$$\left(\frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_l} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_h} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right)^{-1}$$

where, ω_ν - ν mode frequency; ν includes: polarization index $|s, p|$.

\mathbf{v}_\perp - holes velocity;

$\varepsilon^{\vec{r}}$ - dielectric constant; the mode cross structure is determined by wave vectors – continuous ones

\bar{q}, \tilde{q} for l, r modes, and discrete \tilde{k} - for L (localized) mode;

a_r, a_l the amplitude of right-incident (r) or left-incident (l) wave;

$m_{l,h}$ - for light ($n=l$) and heavy ($n'=h$) holes respectively;

$$\theta = \hat{\vec{p}, \vec{p}'} = \frac{1}{m_l} - \frac{1}{m_h} = \frac{1}{\eta_-}$$

Energy flux \bar{S} dynamic restores the state of maximum symmetry from the state of symmetry breaking, which leads to ‘vacuum state.’

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

i. Considered here is the new bosonic mechanism for describing the obtaining of masses by bosons. This mechanism is constructed upon a model of massless gravitational-dark field acquires mass due to the spontaneous symmetry breaking (which is understood in the context of changing between ‘mixed’ and ‘pure’ states of gauge field, ref. item 2, chapter ‘Introduction’) and the contribution of matter; and the hypothesis that the dark energy is represented as an energy of a dark field in a single gravitational-dark field.

ii. The model describes massive gravitational and dark fields and their interaction with the vector field based on the Fierz-Pauli approach.

iii. Gauge bosons acquire masses as a result of the interaction with a massive combined gravitational- dark field.

iv. Specified how fermions obtain mass as a consequence of the application of the mass-generation mechanism of the noted theory to fermions.

The theory addressed experimentally measurable related quantity, as e.g., the weak fermionic mixing angle.

v. The following is an explanation of the physical meaning of the terms of eq. (2.6.1 b) in the context of changing between ‘mixed’ and ‘pure’ states of gauge field:

a) in the ‘mixed’ state the representation (gravitational-dark field eq. (A 2.1.1)- (A 2.1.2)) is reduced to case characterized by scalar mode. This corresponds to the Higgs model.

➤ gauge vector boson mass term is determined by $-\frac{3}{8}B_l B_l^* C C^*$ (ref. eq. (2.6.1 b)), where C is

in the form of eq. (A 2.1.2); $-\frac{3}{4}k^2 C^* C$ is the corresponding free-field term;

b) in the ‘pure’ state the representation (gravitational-dark field eq. (A 2.1.1)- (A 2.1.2)) is reduced to case characterized by tensor mode. This corresponds to ‘the new bosonic mechanism’ model.

➤ gauge vector boson mass term is determined by $B_l B_l^* A_{ik} A_{ik}^*$ (ref. eq. (2.6.1 b)), where A_{ik} is in the form of eq. (A 2.1.0); $k^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik}$ is the corresponding free-field term.

vi. Two major point of overlap between the mechanism and general relativity theory:

a) Equation of motion eq. (1.3.0 a) for massless dark field inline with Einstein eq. omitting matter provided.

b) In the case of a massless gravitational field symmetry Lagrangian eq. (1.4.1 b) ,

the EOM (eq. (A.1), ref. [2])) addresses Einstein eq. omitting matter precisely.

IV. CONCLUSION

i. 'The meaning of the spontaneous symmetry breaking' is understood in the context of spontaneous changing between 'mixed' and 'pure' states of gauge field which appears in the framework of the outlined mechanism and can apply to global and local symmetry without violating the constraint denoted by Elitzur theorem [6].

ii.

a) The existence of the hierarchy mass gap and changing states of gauge field denoted (ref. Fig. A4, below) addresses issue of the difference between energy density of dark energy and gauge boson masses(calculations based on [2] give a value of 100 GeV compatible with collider experiment).

b)The scalar term is obtained within the scope of the presented approach and is included as a part of the mathematical expression, which describes obtaining mass by vector gauge boson. The noted scalar has properties consistent with the properties of Higgs scalar observed in the Standard Model.

c)The existence of dark boson is predicted. This boson is manifested at the same time as a quant of dark field and as a gauge boson of interaction between particles of dark matter. Prediction of dark boson points out on the experimental testability of the theory.

d) Dark field represents the fifth dimension possessing a dark-like Killing field with a conserved quantity dark energy.

iii. The presented model contributes to Lorentz violation as a result of taking into account dark sector, which leads to the appearance of corresponding terms in symmetries Lagrangian of the theory.

iv. The renormalizability of the theory symmetries Lagrangian addressed. (Ref., also [2], [31]). Theory Lagrangian for the outlined mechanism is described by the formula eq. (2.6.1 b).

v. Constraints on the theory presented, which addresses the possibility of introducing gravitational - dark field with mass 100 GeV.

vi. Dark matter(particle) constitutes the structure explicitly described in ref. Fig. A4.1.

vii. Addressed matter-antimatter asymmetry appears due to processing antimatter into matter according to connection (A 6.1).

viii. Correspondences (A 6.1) and (A 6.2) comprise a common (unified) connection and basis for postulate **P2**.

With existence condition formulated as postulate **P1**.

Experimental proof based on testing noted correspondences, namely:

For (A 6.1), include the dark boson Ξ particle with negative energy [2], thus pointing out the gravity manipulation effect. Verification of existence of dark boson with properties of negative gravitational mass and positive inertial mass would address to mechanism of generation mass due to positive inertial mass and violation equivalence principle in general relativity due to negative gravitational mass.

For (A 6.2) include the presence of a gravitational wave, thus representing experimentally measured value.

In the theoretical framework, these connections also denote the process of restoring global symmetry in the mechanism due to the transition from 'pure' state to 'mixed' state.

APPENDICES

A1. On the subject of fermion masses.

Within the framework of the specified mechanism the general consideration appears for the Yukawa coupling term as following [5]:

$$-L_{Yukawa}(\Phi, \left| \begin{matrix} \varphi^D \\ \varphi^M \end{matrix} \right.) = \left| \varphi^D \right. \overline{g\varphi^D} \Phi \varphi^D = \overline{g\varphi^D} \left[C + (t_{ii}^{-1} \delta_k^i + g^{ik}) A_{ik} \right] \varphi^D \quad (\text{A 1.1})$$

where

φ^D denotes Dirac field;

φ^M denotes Majorana field.

Substituting eqs. (1.1 b) and (A 2.1 below) into eq. (A 1.1), obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} -L_{Yukawa}(\Phi, \left| \begin{matrix} \varphi^D \\ \varphi^M \end{matrix} \right.) &= \overline{g\varphi^D} C \varphi^D + \overline{g\varphi^D} (t_{ii}^{-1} \delta_k^i + g^{ik}) A_{ik} \varphi^D = \\ &g\nu \overline{\varphi^D} \varphi^D + g \left[\xi + (t_{ii}^{-1} \delta_k^i + g^{ik}) A_{ik} \right] \overline{\varphi^D} \varphi^D \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A 1.2})$$

In eq. (A 1.2) first term is the mass term for a fermion with mass $g\nu$ appears due to the mechanism of spontaneous symmetry breaking. This means the coupling constant g is directly proportional to the fermion's mass.

Dirac (Majorana) field interaction with tensor- gravitational and goldstone-dark components of scalar field Φ is denoted in the second term.

A2. Symmetries Lagrangian of the presented theory.

Consider an expression for symmetries Lagrangian from which equations in full nonlinear form are derived.

Let us consider eq. (1.4.1 a) and compare it with eq. (A 2.0) (general form of eq. (1.2.1 a)).

$$L_{FP} = k^2 A_{ik} A_{ik} + \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} - 2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}}{\partial x_s} - \frac{3}{4} k^2 C^2 - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} \quad (\text{A 2.0})$$

According to the approach developed in ref. chapter ‘Abelian symmetry breaking’, paragraph ‘Before symmetry breaking’, the following correspondence exists:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{case } \phi_i = 0 \mid C_{ijk}^i = 0 & \text{case } \phi_i \neq 0 \mid C_{ijk}^i \neq 0 \\ i\Pi_k = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} & i\Pi_k = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} - ie\phi_k \\ \text{contr}(A_{ik}) = \iota_{ii}\Xi & A_{ik} = ih_{ik} \\ C = \nu + \xi & C = \nu + \xi + i\xi^i \end{array} \quad (\text{A 2.1})$$

where a wave-field A_{ik} is a symmetrical tensor of the second rank (ref. Fierz-Pauli); C is an auxiliary scalar field.

➤ ➤ Renormalizability:

By substituting eqs. (A 2.1) correspondently into mass terms for eqs. (1.4.1 a) and (A 2.0):

∴ case $\phi_i = 0$

compare eq. (0.1.1) and mass term for eq. (A 2.0) and by virtue of Goldstone theorem ($k_\xi = 0$) and ref. eq. (1.3 a), obtain

$$2\lambda\Xi^2\nu^2 = k_\Xi^2 \left(\langle g^{ik} \rangle \right)^2 A_{ik}^2 \quad (\text{A 2.2.1})$$

i.e. $k_\Xi \sim \sqrt{\lambda}\nu$ (if quartic interaction terms are omitted and the constant terms are contracted), masses for dark field (ref. eq. (1.3 b)) are obtained.

∴ case $\phi_i \neq 0$

from eq. (ref. [27]) of complex massless boson field coupled minimally with an electromagnetic field (compare eq. (0.1.2)) and eq. (1.4.1 a) by virtue of dark field, which does not interact with electromagnetic field, therefore Goldstone-dark field can be omitted altogether, and the following is obtained

$$\frac{1}{2}(\partial h_{ik} + eA_{ik}\nu)^2 = k_h^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik} \quad (\text{A 2.2.2})$$

then ref. eq. (1.5), obtain masses for gravitational field $k_h \sim e\nu$.

Thus, it is confirmed that mass terms in FP eqs. (A 2.0) and (1.4.1 a) and eqs. (1.3 b) and (1.5) correspond and have the same values.

This correspondence is a proof that current theory symmetries Lagrangian eq. (1.4.1 c) (\leftrightarrow eq. (1.5)) is of Φ^4 type.

(The replacement of the original symmetries Lagrangian by one for scalars only is an approximation.)

∠ Renormalizability of the interacting symmetries Lagrangians in four space-time dimensions, which contains a symmetric tensor field eq. (1.4.1 c), is proved in five dimensions. The existence of the fifth dimension appears as a required mathematical condition for the symmetries Lagrangian of the theory to be renormalizable. ■

∠ Based on the following facts FP symmetries Lagrangian eq. (A 2.0) is a non interactive limit of eq. (1.4.1 a) . ■

∠ Therefore, follows the conclusion that eq. (1.4.1 a) is sought for symmetries Lagrangian. (The mechanism of appearing mass terms in FP eqs. (A 2.0) and (1.4.1 a) is specified in ref. chapter ‘Abelian symmetry breaking’).

In the framework of the specified mechanism:

i) dark field represents the fifth dimension possessing a dark-like Killing field, which breaks the symmetry into four dimensions. As follows from the notes (ref. [28-30]), this dimension can be introduced in a non-contradictory way that is still referenced from a physical standpoint to four dimensions.

The physics of the fifth dimension appears as a Lorentz violation;

ii) dark-like Killing field corresponds to the conserved quantity, i.e. dark energy.

∠ Thus, the renormalizability of the theory is formulated in the five-dimensional space.

Proving renormalizability of the presented theory is based on renormalizability of theories with spontaneously broken symmetries (ref. [31]). ■

The proof that Lagrangian of the theory (ref. eq. 1.4.1a) corresponds to the special cases (ref. [31]) is outlined in ref. eqs. (A 2.2.1), (A 2.2.2).

A3. Considering of non-minimal coupling.

In additional terms the fields h, ζ, ϕ_i in eq. (1.5) appear, i.e. (this approximation holds in the case of minimal electromagnetic coupling)

$$L_{h-\zeta}^1 = \sqrt{2}e\phi_i\zeta(\partial_i h + e\nu\phi_i) - \sqrt{2}e\phi_i h(\partial_i \zeta + e\nu\phi_i) + \sqrt{2}e^2\phi_i^2\nu h$$

$$L_{h-\zeta}^2 = e^2\phi_i^2(\zeta^2 + h^2)$$
(A 3.1)

To retain a correct number of degrees of freedom for spin 2 field, non minimal interaction term is to appear [32]

$$L_{nonmin} = 4^{-1}ieh_{i\alpha}F^{\alpha\beta}h_{\beta}^i$$
(A 3.2)

A4. Mass scale structure and the mathematical connections diagram.

1.1 The following diagram depicts mass scales (in order of magnitude) in the framework of the specified mechanism.

Fig. A4 Mass scales and corresponding symmetries.

Mathematical definitions below are used to describe the following expressions:

a) the ‘mixed’ \rightarrow ‘pure’ state transition is defined by

$$\langle P_n | L_{FP_{pure}} | P_n \rangle \geq \langle P_0 | L_{FP_{mixed}} | P_0 \rangle + \Delta_n \quad (\text{A 4.1})$$

b) the ‘vacuum’ \rightarrow ‘mixed’ state transition is defined by

$$\langle P_0 | L_{FP_{mixed}} | P_0 \rangle \geq \langle 0 | L_{FP_{vacuum}} | 0 \rangle + \Delta_0 \quad (\text{A 4.2})$$

c) the ‘vacuum’ state $\langle \Phi \rangle \equiv (\langle 0 | \Phi | 0 \rangle) = \nu$ and ‘unbroken’ state $\langle \Phi \rangle \equiv (\langle 0 | \Phi | 0 \rangle) = 0$

define spinor $\langle \Phi \rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \nu \end{pmatrix}$.

\exists empty waves of Ξ -type for ‘vacuum’ state;

where $\langle 0 |$ describes the ground state of sine-Gordon model.

\therefore dark part *s.t.* anti-de Sitter space is sine-Gordon model *s.t.* surface of constant negative curvature.

In these equations, $L_{FP_{pure}}$, $L_{FP_{mixed}}$, $L_{FP_{vacuum}}$ are denoted correspondently by eq. (A 0.1.4.1 a, below) in ‘pure’, ‘mixed’ and ‘vacuum’ states with substitution of (viz. eq. (1.4.1 a) *s.t.* eqs. (A 2.1)) :

(A 0.1.4.1 a)

$$L_{FP} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(k_h^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik}, : A_{ik} = ih_{ik}, \exists \phi_i \neq 0, \eta \mapsto h, \zeta \mapsto \xi \triangleleft \text{'pure'} \right. \\ \left. \left(0, : \exists \phi_i = 0, \eta \mapsto h, \zeta \mapsto \xi \triangleleft \text{'mixed'} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(k_{\Xi}^2 A_{ik}^* A_{ik}, : A_{ik} \mapsto \text{contr}(A_{ik}), -\exists \phi_i, \eta \mapsto \Xi, \zeta \mapsto \Xi \triangleleft \text{'vacuum'} \right) \right) \right\} +$$

$$\frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} + e^2 \phi_l^2 A_{ik} A_{ik}^*$$

$$-2 \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} - 2e^2 \phi_r \phi_s A_{rk} A_{sk}^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} + \frac{1}{2} e^2 \phi_r \phi_k A_{rk} C^* + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} + \frac{1}{2} e^2 \phi_r \phi_k A_{rk}^* C - \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l}$$

$$- \frac{3}{4} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(k_{\xi}^2 C^* C, : C = \nu + \xi + i\xi', \exists \phi_i \neq 0, \eta \mapsto h, \zeta \mapsto \xi \triangleleft \text{'pure'} \right. \\ \left. \left(0, : \exists \phi_i = 0, \eta \mapsto h, \zeta \mapsto \xi \triangleleft \text{'mixed'} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(k_{\Xi}^2 C^* C, : C = \nu + \xi, -\exists \phi_i, \eta \mapsto \Xi, \zeta \mapsto \Xi \triangleleft \text{'vacuum'} \right) \right) \right\}$$

$$- \frac{3}{8} e^2 \phi_l^2 C C^* +$$

$$i \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(e\phi_l A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial A_{ik}}{\partial x_l} - e\phi_l A_{ik} \frac{\partial A_{ik}^*}{\partial x_l} - 2e\phi_s A_{sk}^* \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} + 2e\phi_r A_{rk} \frac{\partial A_{sk}^*}{\partial x_s} + A_{rk} A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial \phi_r}{\partial x_i} - A_{rk} A_{ik}^* \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial x_r} + \frac{1}{2} e\phi_k C^* \frac{\partial A_{rk}}{\partial x_r} - \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} e\phi_r A_{rk} \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_k} - \frac{1}{2} e\phi_k C \frac{\partial A_{rk}^*}{\partial x_r} + \frac{1}{2} e\phi_r A_{rk}^* \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_k} - \frac{3}{8} e\phi_l C^* \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_l} + \frac{3}{8} e\phi_l C \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x_l} \right) \end{array} \right\}$$

The eq. (2.6.1 b) for spin 1 boson and eq. (1.4.1 a) are invariant under the following substitution $B_k \mapsto e\phi_k$ (cf. eq. (1.4.0) and eq. (2.6.0)).

$\langle P_0 |$ solution (below) is orthogonal, normalized and non-invariant under shifts of the scalar η -field.

\therefore this is the evidence of the spontaneous breaking (i.e. $\langle \Phi \rangle \equiv (\langle 0 | \Phi | 0 \rangle) = \nu$) of the field-shift symmetry.

$$ih \frac{\partial P_0(q_0, t; q_0)}{\partial t} \Big|_{t=0} = k_{\pm} P_0(q_0) , \text{ where } i=0 \text{ is 'mixed' state; } P_0 = P_i; i=0$$

$$ih [P_0(q_0)]^{-1} \frac{\partial P_0(q_0, t)}{\partial t} \Big|_{t=0} = k_{\pm} P_0(q_0) : (P_0(q_0, t; q_0) \equiv [P_0(q_0)]^{-1} P_0(q_0, t))$$

ad hoc:

$$P_0(q_0, t) = P_0(q_0) e^{\frac{-itk_{\pm} e^{iq_0}}{\hbar}} , tk_{\pm} \text{ -tuning parameter;}$$

$q_0 \left(\equiv \alpha_l q_{i(l)} \Big|_{t=0}, i=0 \right) : \alpha_l q_{i(l)}$ the measurement of an i -th state; $\alpha_l \mapsto {}^l A$, where ${}^l A \mapsto \eta$ -field shifts.

$\langle P_n |$ is degenerate by $i \in [1, \dots, n]$ (i.e. all vacua are orthogonal to each other, being an orthonormal basis, which prohibits them to be part of a single separable Hilbert space).

i -th state wavefunction $P_i(q_i, t)$ is denoted by:

(A 0.4 a)

$$ih \frac{\partial P_i(q_i, t; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l)}{\partial t} = H_i \left(\equiv \hat{H} P_i \right) , P_0 = P_i; H_i \rightarrow H_0$$

with initial condition $P_i(q_i, 0) = P_i(q_i)$, where $i \in [1, \dots, n]$ are 'pure' states;

$$H = H_0(q_i) + \alpha_l H_i^{\text{int}}(q_i; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l) =$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i e^{iq_i} + \sum_{i=n+1}^m \sum_{b=1}^n m'_i \int_{R_+} P_r^i(y) P_r^*(y) dy e^{iq_b} + \prod_{\lambda=1}^{n-1} \prod_{j=\lambda+1}^n m_j^{\lambda^2} e^{2 \sum_{\lambda=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=\lambda+1}^n q_{\lambda} q_j} \prod_{l=1}^s \prod_{g=1}^n \alpha_l m_g^s e^{-\sum_{l=1}^s \sum_{g=1}^n \alpha_l q_g^2}$$

m_i - number of degenerate of i -th state (orthogonal) on $i \in [1, \dots, n]$ defined by

$$\hat{F}_r^i P_r^i = m_i P_r^i, \quad i \in [1, \dots, n]$$

(\hat{F}_r^i operators of a number of the i -th orthogonal state);

m_i' - number of degenerate of i -th state (non-orthogonal) on $i \in]n, \dots, m]$

(\hat{F}_r^i - operators of number of the i -th non-orthogonal state);

α_l - l -th perturbation is defined on interval $l \in [1, \dots, s]$;

$$h = \frac{1}{q_i^{-1} \left(\frac{\pi}{l} \right)}$$

ad hoc:

$$P_i(q_i, t; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l) = e^{\frac{-itH_i}{h}} P_i(q_i, 0), \quad P_i(q_i, 0) = e^{iq_i}$$

In reference to the subject of the stochastic structure of spacetime, consideration of nonlocality accounting for an electromagnetic field applying to i -th state measurement, points to the connection with Bell's theorem and the direction of measurement:

(A 0.4 b)

$$\bar{q}_i = \int_0^{q_i^{-1} \left(\frac{\pi}{l} \right)} \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[\begin{array}{l} P^{* \text{superstate}}(\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_n, t; \alpha_l) (-ih\nabla_i) P^{\text{superstate}}(\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_n, t; \alpha_l) \\ -P^{\text{superstate}}(\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_n, t; \alpha_l) (-ih\nabla_i) P^{* \text{superstate}}(\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_n, t; \alpha_l) \end{array} \right] \\ \times \frac{1}{\left| P^{\text{superstate}}(\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_n, t; \alpha_l) \right|^2} - e^{\bar{\phi}_i} \end{array} \right\} dt$$

where $q_i \rightarrow \bar{q}_i$ in

$$P^{\text{superstate}}(q_1, \dots, q_n, t; \alpha_l) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i(q_i, t; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l) = \sum_{i=1}^n e^{\frac{-itH_i}{h}} P_i(q_i, 0)$$

\succ thus defines dependence on $\bar{\phi}_i$.

The approach specified determines the path for chosen initial q_0 (a) and final quantum states ${}^{\alpha_l} q_{i(t)}$ (b) that satisfy:

preselection boundary conditions (a); and

does not require specifying the postselection condition (b) by defining a path as trajectory q_i associated with a specific quantum state.

Viz. measurement q_i , $i \in [1, \dots, n]$ denote time series $q(t)$; this function has stochastic non-Markov features and defined by an autoregressive process to extrapolate preselection values to known measurable q_i postselection values with time-dependent error terms represented by a heteroskedastic approximation:

$$q(t) = \mu(t) + F(t) + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i q(t-i) + \sum_{i=1}^l \theta_i F(t-i)$$

where

$$\mu^i(t) = \langle q_i \rangle = \int P_i^*(q_i, t; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l) q_i P_i(q_i, t; q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n, \alpha_l) d(q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}, \dots, q_n);$$

error terms are defined by

$$F(t) = \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i B^i \right) q(t)$$

B_i -backshift operator;

solving θ_i from system

$$q(t) - F(t) \approx [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_l] \begin{bmatrix} F_{t-1} \\ \vdots \\ F_{t-l} \end{bmatrix};$$

solving φ_i, μ from Yule-Walker eq.;

$p = 2l$ by Akaike's information criterion.

Posteselection values are:

$$\alpha_i q_{i(t)} = {}^l A \int_{t_0}^t q_i(\tau) J_0(t-\tau) d\tau$$

where $q_i(\tau) = {}^i q(t), t = \tau$;

${}^l A$ - - shock wave amplitude.

➤ The notion of changing the fine-structure constant (in this approach Dirac const depends on q_i) reflect the existence of a massless field that couples to matter [33].

Noted is the source of appearance in 'unbroken' state gravitational- dark field in theory. ■

The Dirac const fine-tuned with tuning parameter tk_{Ξ} and the massless field appears non-contradictory as gravitational part (Lorentz invariant) in the combined gravitational-dark field eq. (1.1 a).

1. According to Lowenstein extension [34] this massless scalar field renormalizable.
2. Moving between ‘unbroken’ state to ‘vacuum’ state is described by the applicability of Zimmermann identity to linear symmetry transformations.

➤ ➤ Constraints:

1. Thus changing the geometry of spacetime and corresponding symmetries denoted by changing states of gauge field (ref. Fig. A4) point out on existing mass gap as the mechanism of cancellation difference between energy density of dark energy and gauge boson masses. Specifically scale factor of CPT invariance $\sim 10^{14}$ GeV account for cancellation differences in energy scales between energy density of dark energy and gauge boson masses. In the theory framework CPT violation is associated with changing symmetries.

2. The quantitative analysis follows from the description of the geometrical structure underlying the theory [2].

In this framework, the gravitational-dark field is represented in two components, also ref. Postulates P1, P2.

The first component (mass part) corresponds to the gravitational tensor component, with mass/energy equates to the value of energy density of dark energy, which constrained to 10^{-12} eV.

The second -WIMP component (tunnel part) corresponds to the scalar component with mass/energy equates to the value of 'Higgs like' mass constrained to 100 GeV.

Constraint on WIMP as 100 GeV follows from [35].

Fig. A4.1 Fiber bundle (fiber – dark part, base - gravitational part) hypersaddle and hypersphere represent dark part and gravitational part correspondently.

⤵ The two parts are geometrically bundled on hyperkähler manifold through metric tensor g_{ik} , where covariant form transforms address to scalar >tensor map and contravariant form transforms address to tensor>scalar map [2].

The scalar part addressed to the fifth dimension, while tensor part three dimensional. Time spans over all five dimensions, while in the fifth dimension time series is asymptotically zero.

The mass of the gravitational-dark field $\eta(x)$ is represented by its scalar constraint, i.e., 100 GeV.

⤵ The geometry (ref. Fig. A4.1) addresses dark matter structure, with charge noted by [2], [36]. The mass part refers to R-N metrics.

Dark matter structures can annihilate when geometrically opposed to each other, so two gamma quants can appear (ref. [35]).

A5. The weak fermionic mixing angle.

The first item to be considered in this context is neutral current, which is mediated by Z -boson (γ - photon behavior is analog to it).

Column vector for neutral currents is denoted as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix}$$

The second item to be considered is charged current, which is mediated by W^+ , W^- bosons. Column vector for charged currents is denoted as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} W^+ \\ W^- \end{bmatrix}$$

Neutral to charged column vectors can be mapped as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} W^+ \\ W^- \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} Z \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = W^0 \begin{bmatrix} e^{i\phi^+} \\ e^{i\phi^-} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A 5.1})$$

where W^0 (complex) charged field multiplier.

The eq. (A 5.1) under the condition: $\varphi^- = \frac{\pi}{2} + \varphi^+$ (W^- antiparticle), will lead to the following:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W^0 \cos \varphi^+ + iW^0 \sin \varphi^+ \\ -W^0 \sin \varphi^+ + iW^0 \cos \varphi^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varphi^+ & \sin \varphi^+ \\ -\sin \varphi^+ & \cos \varphi^+ \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} W^0 \\ iW^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A 5.2})$$

Eq. (A 5.2) represents the connection between neutral and charged currents.

Since \mathbb{C} is a 2-dimensional vector space of $\mathbb{R} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ i \end{bmatrix}$ becomes a basis for \mathbb{C} / \mathbb{R} representing charged vector bosons.

A6. Dark matter(particle) and baryon asymmetry.

In reference to Fig. A4.1 (Appendix A4), the geometry has no charge in the 'mixed' state massless due to the state of symmetry being global but charged in the 'pure' state massive due to the spontaneous breaking of local symmetry.

The annihilation (address to 'mixed' state) of dark matter structures leads to the appearance (address to 'pure' state) of:

- 1) two gamma quants γ^2 with summary spin $s_{\Sigma} = 0$;
- 2) two gamma quants γ^2 with summary spin $s_{\Sigma} = 2$

Combining two photons with spins adds constructively or destructively obtain stable configuration 1); and not stable configuration 2).

Fig. A6.1 Geometrically opposed two dark matter structures.

> Correspondences and connections.

This addresses the issues of introducing a dark field (A 6.1) and the appearance of a gravitational field (A 6.2) in the theoretical framework.

Combined (A 6.1) and (A 6.2) connections, which incorporate gravitational and dark fields, constitute the basis for postulate **P2**.

$$\gamma^2_{s_\Sigma=0} e^+ \rightarrow e^- \Xi \quad (\text{A 6.1})$$

$$g_{ik} \gamma^2_{s_\Sigma=2} e^- \rightarrow e^- h_{ik} \quad (\text{A 6.2})$$

where Ξ (ref. [2], with negative energy) dark boson possessing negative gravitational mass and positive inertial mass,

$h(g^{ik} h_{ik})$ tensor-graviton,

$E_\gamma \sim 60$ GeV (thus combined energy corresponds to the energy of a Higgs-like scalar),

$$E_{e^+} \approx E_{e^-};$$

described by the formula eq. (2.6.1 b), which is detailed for 'mixed' and 'pure' states in the formula eq. (A 0.1.4.1 a).

The increase of ~ 40 GeV in the combined energy of two dark matter structures (of energy $E \sim 100$ GeV each) is due to a triggered interaction with the ambient gravitational-dark field, where the dark matter structures absorb energy from this field.

Thus, total energy is $E_{tot} \sim 240$ GeV (consistent with the VEV of the Higgs field).

Connection (A 6.1) denotes processing antimatter into matter, thus to condition matter-antimatter asymmetry.

\therefore

The decay process restores the state of global symmetry, thus moving back from the 'pure' state to the 'mixed' state.

< Noted correspondences represent underlying unification connections and imply experimental proof.

Gravitational-dark structure.

1. Connections (A 6.1) and (A 6.2) are mathematical formulations of the gravitational-dark field. They represent the “paired” state as doubled gravitational-dark structures.

Each structure constitutes a splitting of the Higgs scalar mass $\sim 125.1 \text{ Gev}$ into the dark part of 120 Gev addressing the dark boson, which is a quant of dark field, and establishes the 10^{-12} eV dark energy floor and 5.1 Gev as the intrinsic mass of the gravitational part. This mass part is required to anchor the dark boson to 4D space-time.

The 3.11 Gev is the base gravitational mass before energy absorption; represents the "mixed" gauge field state.

This binding energy accounts for (ref. Fig. A6.1) and approximates the VEV of the Higgs field:

$$(2 \times 120 \text{ Gev}) + (2 \times 3.11 \text{ Gev approx. scaling}) \approx 246.22 \text{ Gev}$$

2. The excess of 20 Gev is discrete “quantum jump” in the energy for a single structure addresses energy flux through the dark part (tunnel), ref. Fig. A4.1.

This theoretical “signature” calculated difference between the value of 'Higgs like' mass constrained to 100 Gev and dark boson mass:

$$120 \text{ Gev} - 100 \text{ Gev} = 20 \text{ Gev}$$

This “signature” is directly related to the transition of the gauge field from a “mixed” state to a “pure” state.

The difference between 3.11 Gev and 5.1 Gev is the activation energy of the gravitational anchor. The 3.11 Gev addresses the "mixed" state, and the 5.1 Gev addresses the "pure" state. The transition between these states involves the absorption of energy from the ambient gravitational field.

Analysis of the proposed reaction (eq. A 6.1).

Initial state

Two photons:

Energy: $E_{\gamma 1} = 60 \text{ GeV}$, $E_{\gamma 2} = 60 \text{ GeV}$

Total energy:

$E_{\text{initial}} = 60 \text{ GeV} + 60 \text{ GeV} + E_{e^+}$

Spin: Each photon has a spin of 1. Their sum is 0, which means their spin vectors are anti-parallel.

Momentum: Photons have energy $E = pc$, where c is the speed of light. Their momenta are anti-parallel, so $p_{\gamma 1} = -p_{\gamma 2}$. The magnitude of each photon's momentum is $p_{\gamma} = E_{\gamma}/c = 60 \text{ GeV}/c$.

Positron:

Energy: E_{e^+}

Spin: $1/2$

Charge: $+1$

Lepton number: -1

Final state

Electron:

Energy: E_{e^-}

Spin: $1/2$

Charge: -1

Lepton number: $+1$

Dark boson particle Ξ :

Energy: $E_{\Xi} = 120 \text{ GeV}$

Spin: 0

Charge: $+2$

Lepton number: -2

Baryon number: 0

\therefore

The reaction requires a change of lepton number $\Delta L = 2$, meaning a process that violates total lepton number.

Conservation laws check (eq. A 6.1).

Conservation of Charge:

Initial charge:

$$q\gamma_1 + q\gamma_2 + qe^+ = 0 + 0 + (+1) = +1$$

Final charge:

$$qe^- + q\Xi = (-1) + (+2) = +1$$

Charge is conserved.

Conservation of Lepton Number:

Initial lepton number:

$$L\gamma_1 + L\gamma_2 + Le^+ = 0 + 0 + (-1) = -1$$

Final lepton number:

$$Le^- + L\Xi = (+1) + (-2) = -1$$

Lepton number is conserved.

Conservation of Baryon Number:

Initial baryon number:

$$B\gamma_1 + B\gamma_2 + Be^+ = 0 + 0 + 0 = 0$$

Final baryon number:

$$Be^- + B\Xi = 0 + 0 = 0$$

Baryon number is conserved.

Conservation of Spin:

Initial spin: The two photons have anti-parallel spins of 1, resulting in a total spin of 0. The positron has a spin of 1/2.

Final spin: The electron has a spin of 1/2. The dark boson particle Ξ has spin 0.

Spin can be conserved.

Conservation of Energy:

Initial energy:

$$E_{initial} = 60 \text{ GeV} + 60 \text{ GeV} + E_{e^+} = 120 \text{ GeV} + E_{e^+}$$

Final energy:

$$E_{final} = E_{e^-} + E_{\Xi} = E_{e^-} + 120 \text{ GeV}$$

By conservation of energy,

$$120 \text{ GeV} + E_{e^+} = E_{e^-} + 120 \text{ GeV}, \text{ which means } E_{e^+} = E_{e^-}.$$

Energy can be conserved.

Conservation of Momentum:

Initial momentum:

$p^{\vec{initial}} = p^{\vec{\gamma}1} + p^{\vec{\gamma}2} + p^{\vec{e}+}$. Since the photons are anti-parallel, their total momentum is zero, so $p^{\vec{initial}} = p^{\vec{e}+}$.

Final momentum: $p^{\vec{final}} = p^{\vec{e}-} + p^{\vec{\Xi}}$.

By conservation of momentum,

$$p^{\vec{e}+} = p^{\vec{e}-} + p^{\vec{\Xi}}.$$

Momentum can be conserved.

Thus, can establish the following relationship for the momentum and energy:

$$p^{\vec{e}+} = p^{\vec{e}-} + p^{\vec{\Xi}}$$

The total energy of the positron must equal the total energy of the electron, so $Ee^+ = Ee^-$.

∴

Complement.

In the case of the interaction of a normal particle with a dark boson, both particles unidirectionally accelerate, but conservation of total energy and momentum is maintained. This is because the dark boson has negative energy and momentum that balance the positive energy and momentum of the normal particle.

Conservation laws check (eq. A 6.2).

Conservation of Charge:

Initial charge:

$$qg_{ik} + q\gamma_1 + q\gamma_2 + qe^- = 0 + 0 + 0 + (-1) = -1$$

Final charge:

$$qe^- + qh_{ik} = (-1) + 0 = -1$$

Charge is conserved.

Conservation of Lepton Number:

Initial lepton number:

$$Lg_{ik} + L_{\gamma 1} + L_{\gamma 2} + L_{e^-} = 0 + 0 + 0 + (+1) = +1$$

Final lepton number:

$$L_{e^-} + Lh_{ik} = (+1) + 0 = +1$$

Lepton number is conserved.

Conservation of Baryon Number:

Initial baryon number:

$$Bg_{ik} + B\gamma_1 + B\gamma_2 + Be^- = 0 + 0 + 0 = 0$$

Final baryon number:

$$B_{e^-} + Bh_{ik} = 0 + 0 = 0$$

Baryon number is conserved.

Conservation of Spin:

Spin: Each photon has a spin of 1. Their sum is 2, which means their spin vectors are parallel.

Their momenta are parallel, so $p\gamma_1 = p\gamma_2$.

Initial spin:

Spin 2 (g_{ik}), spin 2 (coupled photons $S_{\Sigma} = 2$), then range $|2 - 2| = 0$ to $2 + 2 = 4$

e^-

Total initial spin:

$$1/2, 3/2, 5/2, 7/2, 9/2$$

Final spin:

e^-

Spin 2 (η_{ik})

$$\text{then range } |2 - 1/2| = 3/2 \quad \text{to} \quad 2 + 1/2 = 5/2$$

Total final spin:

$$3/2, 5/2$$

Match exists; spin is conserved.

Conservation of Energy:

Initial energy:

$$E(g_{ik}) + E(\gamma^2) + E(e^-)$$

Final energy:

$$E(e^-) + E(\eta_{ik})$$

By conservation of energy,

$$E(g_{ik}) + E(\gamma^2) + E(e^-) = E(e^-) + E(\eta_{ik})$$

which means, $E(g_{ik}) + E(\gamma^2) = E(\eta_{ik})$.

Energy can be conserved.

Conservation of Momentum:

Initial momentum:

$$P_{\gamma 1}^{\mu} + P_{\gamma 2}^{\mu} + P_{e^- (initial)}^{\mu}$$

Final momentum:

$$P_{e^- (final)}^{\mu} + P_{h_{ik}}^{\mu}$$

By conservation of momentum,

$$P_{\gamma 1}^{\mu} + P_{\gamma 2}^{\mu} + P_{e^- (initial)}^{\mu} = P_{e^- (final)}^{\mu} + P_{h_{ik}}^{\mu}, \text{ where}$$

P^{μ} is four-momenta.

Momentum can be conserved.

REFERENCES

- [1] P W Higgs, Phys. Rev. Lett. 13: 508-509((1964).
- [2] R. Taratuta, HAL: hal-01162606 (2015), HAL: hal- 03511680 (2022).
- [3] V. Fierz and W. Pauli, Proc. Roy. Soc. London. A **173**, 211-232 (1939).
- [4] B. de Wit and D. Freedman, Phys.Rev. D **21**, 358-367 (1980).
- [5] S. Elitzur, Phys. Rev. D **12**, 3978-3982 (1975).
- [6] Ivo van Vulpen (2014) <http://www.niknef.nl/~ivov/HiggsLectureNote.pdf> [accessed 2014, June 6].
- [7] F. Mandl and G. Shaw, Quantum Field Theory (Wiley, 2010).
- [8] J. Rosen, Comment: The symmetry principle, Entropy **7**, 308-313 (2005).
- [9] M. Kachelrieß, Advanced Quantum Field Theory (Department of Physics, NTNU Trondheim Norway, 2010).
- [10] G. 't Hooft, arXiv: hep-th/0708.3184 (2008).
- [11] M. Baker and R. Steinke, arXiv:hep-th/9905375v2(2000).
- [12] B. Janssen, From Fierz-Pauli to Einstein-Hilbert (Gravity as a special relativistic field theory, UGR & CAFPE, 2006).
- [13] S. Deser, General Relativity and Gravitation **1**, 9-18 (1970).
- [14] B. Altschul, Q. G. Bailey and A. Kostelecky, arXiv: gr-qc/0912.4852 (2009).
- [15] F. Zwicky, Cosmic and terrestrial tests for the rest mass of gravitons, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific **73**, 314-317 (1961).
- [16] S. Fujita, T. Kimura and Y. Zheng, Found. Phys. **21**, 1117- 1130 (1991).
- [17] S. Coleman and J. Mandula, Phys. Rev. **159**, 1251-1256 (1967).
- [18] G. Fodor, P. Forgács and P. Grandclément, Relativity and Gravitation **157**, 53-60 (2014).
- [19] G. Rosen, Europhys. Lett. **89**, 19002 (2010).
- [20] G. Rosen, Proceeding of the International Workshop on Physics and Mathematics (IWPM 2011).
- [21] G. Rosen, J. Math. Phys.**6**, 1269 - 1272 (1965).
- [22] G. Rosen, J. Math. Phys.**8**, 573 – 575 (1967).
- [23] A.I. Vainshtein, Phys. Lett. **39B**, 393-394 (1972).
- [24] D.G. Boulware and S. Deser, Phys. Rev. D **6**, 3368-3382 (1972).
- [25] V.G. Barjachtar and S.V. Peletminsky, Proceeding of Colleges. Radio-physics 6, 1115 (1963).
- [26] V.F. Hantmacher and I.B. Levinson, Scattering of Charge Carriers in Metals and Semiconductors (Moscow: Nauka, 1984).
- [27] C. Itzykson and J-B. Zuber, Quantum Field Theory (McGraw-Hill, 1980).
- [28] E. Witten, arXiv: hist-ph/1401.8048 v1 (2014).
- [29] E. Cremmer and J. Scherk, Nuclear Physics B **103**, 399-425 (1976).
- [30] E. Cremmer and J. Scherk, Nuclear Physics B **108**, 409-416 (1976).
- [31] T. Banks, Modern Quantum Field Theory A Concise Introduction (Cambridge University Press, 2008).
- [32] C.R. Hagen, Phys. Rev. D **6**, 984-987 (1972).
- [33] J.-P. Uzan, arXiv: astro-ph.CO/1009.5514 (2011).
- [34] J. H. Lowenstein and W. Zimmermann, Comm. Math. Phys. **44**, 73-86 (1975).
- [35] J. Wang, S. Bose, C.S. Frenk, et al., Nature 585.7823, 39-42 (2020).
- [36] J. B. Muñoz, A. Loeb, Nature 557, 684–686 (2018).